

Schrodinger Equation Versus Classical Action Approach to Finding a Propagator (Oscillator Example)

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In (1), a method for finding the propagator of a generalized quantum oscillator directly from the time-dependent Schrodinger equation is presented. This method assumes the form $Q(t)\exp[i(B(t)xx + A(t)yy + C(t)xy)]$ which is inserted into the Schrodinger equation. The equation is broken into purely imaginary and real parts. Time dependent coefficients of xx , xy and yy are found leading to four differential equations which may be solved to ultimately yield a full solution for the propagator.

In (2), it is suggested that the propagator is given by $Q(t) \exp(i \int_{t=0}^{Tf} Lc dt)$. In order to use this approach, a solution to the classical Lagrangian Lc is found and x written as: $XA(Tf-t)+YB(t-0)$ where X and Y are the initial and final x positions (and are numbers). Thus, dx/dt may be computed, and the classical action integral $(t=0 \text{ to } Tf) Lc dt$ found through integration.

In this note, we consider the quantum oscillator and try to demonstrate the two approaches are the same. A key point is that $-i\partial/\partial t$ (partial) in the Schrodinger equation really represents $-i\partial/\partial Tf$ (partial).

Schrodinger Equation Approach

In (1), the propagator is found by assuming the form:

$$Q(t) \exp[i (B(t)XX + A(t)YY + C(t)XY)] \quad ((1))$$

and inserting it into the generalized oscillator Schrodinger equation:

$$i \partial/\partial t (\text{partial}) W(x,t) = -a(t) \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} + b(t)xx W - i(c(t) x \frac{dW}{dx} + d(t)W) \quad ((2))$$

(In (1), two extra potential terms are added, but we do not consider those here. They give rise to non-quadratic type terms e.g. x , y or pure t which means generalizing ((1)) to include these terms).

After inserting ((1)) into ((2)), coefficients of xx , yy and xy are collected and differential equations linear in d/dt are obtained. Note: The Schrodinger equation operator only acts on X . The purely imaginary term associated with xx links $Q(t)$ and $B(t)$. Three other differential equations are obtained. One involves only dB/dt and $B(t)$ while the other two are mixed. It is possible to solve for $B(t)$ and then find $Q(t)$ from the "imaginary" differential equation. Finally, $A(t)$ and $C(t)$ may be obtained. Specific details are provided in (1) for different forms of $a(t)$, $b(t)$, $c(t)$ and $d(t)$.

In this note, we are interested in the oscillator equation:

$$i \frac{d}{dt} \text{partial } W = -1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W + \frac{1}{2} k \text{ xx } W \quad ((3))$$

The same method of (1) may be employed. We consider the differential equation corresponding to the real part of coefficient of xx i.e.

$$dB/dT = -2/m BB - .5k \quad ((4))$$

The known solution of the oscillator propagator is (2):

$$K(x,T,y,0) = \text{sqrt}[mw/ (2*3.14 i \sin(wT))] \exp\{-i.5mw [(xx +yy) \cos(wT)/\sin(wT) - 2xy/\sin(wT)]\}$$

Here T=Tf-Ti with Ti=0 so Tf plays the role of t.

$$B(T) \text{ is thus: } .5mw \cos(wT)/\sin(wT) \quad ((5))$$

One may see that ((5)) satisfies ((4))

Path Integral and Classical Action Approach to the Oscillator Propagator

The propagator may also be obtained using the idea of classical action i.e $Sc = \text{Integral} (t=Ti=0 \text{ to } Tf) Lc \, dt$ where Lc is the classical Lagrangian. This approach does not use the quantum Schrodinger equation. The propagator is given by $B(T) \exp(i Sc)$ where $B(T)$ is calculated using fluctuations of the classical action (see (2)).

We concentrate on $\exp(i Sc)$ to see if one may obtain ((4)) from this approach. The starting point, as in (2), is to find a solution for $x(t)$ to Newton's equation such that $x(Ti) = X$ and $x(Tf) = Y$. Ti will later be taken to be 0. For the oscillator, $\sin(wt)$ and $\cos(wt)$ are solutions of $m \frac{d}{dt} \frac{dx}{dt} = -kx$ so:

$$x(t) = \{ \sin[w(Tf-t)] X + \sin[w(t-Ti)] Y \} / \sin(wT) \quad ((6))$$

$$\text{We write this as: } x(t) = A(Tf-t)/U(T) + B(t-Ti)/U(T) \text{ where } A(t=Ti=0) = U(T) \quad ((7))$$

We let $Ti=0$ so $A(t=0)=U(T)$. Next, the classical action may be calculated using $x(t)$ and $dx(t)/dt$. The classical action coefficient of XX is:

$$B(T) = 1/[U(T)U(T)] \text{ Integral } (t=0 \text{ to } Tf) \frac{dA}{dt} \frac{dA}{dt} .5m - .5k A(Tf-t)A(Tf-t) \, dt \quad ((8))$$

Unlike the quantum case where d/dt means d/dTf , here t is not Tf . In the quantum case, ((4)) yields a DE in dB/dTf so we take d/dTf of ((8)) which involves three parts. First, $U(T)$ has to be differentiated, then $d/dTf \text{ Integral } (0 \text{ to } Tf)$ i.e. Argument of $\text{Integral}(Tf)$ and finally the functions containing Tf within the integral. i.e.

$$dB/dTf = -2 (d/dT U(T)) / [UU] B(Tf) + M dA(t=Tf)/dt dA(t=Tf)/dt / [UU] - 1/[UU] \int_{t=0}^{Tf} [m dA/dt d/dt dA/dt - kA dA/dt] dt \quad ((9))$$

Consider $B = 1/[A(t=0)A(t=0)] \int_{t=0}^{Tf} dA(Tf-t)/dt dA(Tf-t)/dt .5m - .5k A(Tf-t)A(Tf-t) dt$

Where $A(t=0)=U(T)$. Integrating by parts yields:

$$B = 1/[A(t=0)A(t=0)] \{ dA/dt A \text{ (at } t=Tf \text{ and } 0) - \int_{t=0}^{Tf} -A(Tf-t) d/dt dA(Tf-t)/dt m - k AA dt \} \quad ((10))$$

The first term on the RHS of ((10)) is $-dA(t=0)/dt / A(t=0)$ (Note $A(t=Tf)=0$)

In the integral in ((10)), $md/dt dA/dt + kA = 0$ by the equation of motion, so

$$B = (.5m) -dA(t=0)/dt / A(t=0) = -.5m dU/dT / U(T) \quad ((11a))$$

Thus, the first term of ((9)) becomes $-4/m BB$ ((11b))

The second term on the RHS of ((9)) is $m/2 dA/dt(t=Tf)dA/dt(t=Tf) / (U(T)U(T))$ ((11c))

The last term on the RHS of ((9)), using the equation of motion $md/dt dA/dt = -kA$, is equivalent to:

$$+1/[UU] k A A (t=Tf,0) \quad \text{Note: } A(Tf-t) \text{ and } A(t=Tf)=0 \text{ so:}$$

$$-k A(t=0)A(t=0) / [UU] = -k \quad ((12))$$

From the equation of motion: $md/dt dA/dt = -kA$ one has: $dA/dt dA/dt / (ww) + AA = 1$ ((13))

One may use $t=0$ or $t=Tf$ in ((13)). Thus: $dA/dt(t=Tf)= w$ because $A(t=Tf)=0$.

$$((11b)) \text{ becomes: } .5m .5ww/UU \{ dA(t=0)/dt dA(t=0)/dt (1/ww) + A(t=0)A(t=0) \}$$

$$\text{Or } (2/m) BB + .5k$$

Thus, the final result is: $dB/dTf = -2BB - .5 k$ ((14)) which matches ((4)) from the Schrodinger approach.

In order to obtain this result, the Newton equation of motion for the Lagrangian had to be solved and we used the result ((13)) obtained by integrating the equation of motion once to create an identity.

Thus, the Lagrangian approach, using no quantum mechanical equation yields the same result as the approach using the time-dependent Schrodinger equation.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we investigate finding the quantum oscillator propagator using two methods. The first, given in (1), suggests a form of $Q(t) \exp[i (B(t)XX + C(t)YY + D(t)XY)]$ which is inserted into the time-dependent Schrodinger equation. Coefficients of XX are collected to yield a differential equation for $B(t)$. $Q(t)$ is obtained by considering the purely imaginary XX coefficients, $C(t)$ by YY coefficients and $D(t)$, XY coefficients.

In (2), it is suggested that one may evaluate $Q(t)\exp(iS_c)$ where S_c is the classical action given by $\text{Integral}(t_1=0 \text{ to } T_f) L$ where L is the Lagrangian. The Lagrangian is created using: $x(t) = A(T_f-t)/U(T) X + B(t-T_i)/U(T) Y$ and $dx/dt = dA/dt / U(T_f-T_i) X + Y dB/dt / U(T_f-T_i)$ with $A(t=T_f)=0$. These are inserted into the Lagrangian and the integral done from $t=0=T_i$ to $t=T_f$. Taking d/dT_f of the coefficient of XX should yield the same differential equation as obtained in the time-dependent Schrodinger approach. There are three portions to be differentiated, $U(T_f)$, $d/dT_f \text{ Integral}(0, T_f)$ which equals the integral argument evaluated at T_f and terms within the integral containing T_f .

We test this in this note using $A(T_f-t)$ and an equation of motion and find the two agree.

References

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